

Auxfinder - Finding auxiliary variables for imputation models

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Abstract. To deal effectively with missing data, powerful statistical approaches such as MICE and FIML have been developed. To make optimal use of these methods, researchers can include additional variables in the estimation process that are not part of the final analytical model but that improve the prediction of missing values. The selection of these auxiliary variables is often based on theoretical considerations; however, particularly when large datasets are available, a data-driven selection can yield further improvements. We introduce **auxfinder**, a new Stata command that enables users to quickly identify the most promising auxiliary variables.

Keywords: imputation, missing data, MICE, FIML, auxiliary variable, LASSO, Stata

1 Introduction

Missing data constitute a highly prevalent challenge in virtually all empirical research fields, but this problem is particularly pronounced in survey-based studies, which rely on high response rates to obtain adequate data. Even when an individual participates in a survey, item nonresponse is common and can drastically reduce the effective sample size in complex analyses involving many variables. To address these challenges, a variety of statistical techniques have been developed over time. Among the most widely used methods, and those available in Stata, are multiple imputation with chained equations (MICE) and full-information maximum likelihood (FIML) estimation.¹ Especially in the case of MICE, the general approach involves specifying two distinct models that are typically quite similar. The first is the imputation model, which must include all variables with missing values that are to be addressed, although the inclusion of additional variables can be beneficial. After the imputation procedure has been completed, the analytical model is estimated, yielding the results of substantive interest to the researcher.

Nowadays, as researchers have access to fast computers, it is common to build in-

1. How to use auxiliary variables with SEM is explained here: <https://www.stata.com/meeting/new-orleans13/abstracts/materials/nola13-medeiros.pdf>

dividual imputation models for each research project, and potentially even for each specific analysis. Although this approach is more time-consuming, it allows users to carefully tailor their imputations and make optimal use of their data, thereby further improving data quality. One step in this process is optional but offers the potential to incorporate substantial additional information: the inclusion of auxiliary variables. These are variables that are not required in the final analytical model but that improve the imputation process by enhancing the prediction of missing values. In general, there are three main rules for selecting suitable auxiliary variables (Schafer 1997; Graham 2012; Van Buuren and Groothuis-Oudshoorn 2011). First, the variable should have no, or at least very little, missingness itself. In this way, it can contribute information that is not present in the analytical model alone. Second, the variable should be correlated with the missingness of the target variable(s). Third, the variable should be correlated with the target variable itself. As long as at least one of these correlations is sufficiently strong, an auxiliary variable can introduce additional information into the model that was not previously available. Finally, while correlations alone are already a useful indicator, especially in large datasets—where intercorrelations among predictors can be substantial—indiscriminately including all potential auxiliaries is often problematic. Doing so can greatly increase the runtime of the imputation model or lead to convergence failures. Consequently, some researchers recommend estimating a final LASSO model to validate the selection of auxiliary variables (Mainzer et al. 2024). LASSO is a regression approach that can accommodate far more predictors than standard methods and helps to retain only the most relevant ones (Ranstam and Cook 2018).

To illustrate with a simple example, suppose a researcher seeks to understand how a father’s level of education predicts a student’s score on a standardized mathematics test. The analytical model is relatively straightforward: the test score serves as the dependent variable, and the father’s educational attainment is the main independent variable (with additional control variables, such as the student’s gender or a migration background indicator, potentially included). The survey is cross-sectional, so panel attrition is not a concern; however, some fathers were not reachable at the time of data collection, resulting in a substantial proportion of missing values for this key variable. One option would be to include only the main variables in the imputation model and proceed accordingly. However, the imputation can be improved by incorporating relevant auxiliary variables. Two such variables appear particularly useful. The first is a binary item from the student questionnaire indicating whether the parents live together in the same household or apart (for example, following a divorce). Given the definition above, this constitutes a good auxiliary variable because it is reported by the student and therefore has very little missingness. Moreover, it predicts the missingness indicator: when parents live apart, it is much less likely that the father is present in the household at the time of the survey, implying a substantially higher missingness rate for paternal education in non-nuclear families. A second item, also from the student questionnaire, measures the perceived social standing of the family. Although this measure reflects the student’s subjective assessment, it is clearly correlated with the father’s level of education, as education, income, and social status tend to be strongly associated. Consequently, although these two variables are not of direct interest for the main research question and are not included in the analytical model, they constitute

useful auxiliary variables and should be added to the imputation model.

While this example is relatively clear from a theoretical perspective, in practice such variables may not always be directly available, making theory-driven selection more challenging. Nevertheless, as long as relevant correlational structures exist, auxiliary variables can be beneficial. Importantly, the presence of causal relationships is not required.

2 The auxfinder command

2.1 Installation

To install `auxfinder`, type: `net install auxfinder, replace from(https://raw.githubusercontent.com/fbittmann/auxfinder/main/)`.

2.2 Syntax

```
auxfinder varlist [if] [in] , testvars(varlist) [options]
```

2.3 Options

- **testvars**(*varlist*) specifies the variables that are potential candidates as auxiliaries. Factor variable notation is allowed (but omit the `c.` prefix; do not specify interactions). To test all variables in the dataset, use the specifier `_all`. To assess whether a variable is continuous or categorical, the number of levels is used; see the option `catlimit()`. At least one variable must be specified.
- **corrmiss**(*#*) specifies the degree of correlation between the binary missingness indicator of the target variable and the testing variable. A high correlation indicates that a testing variable is able to predict whether a case has a missing value on the target variable, which benefits the imputation procedure. Test variables with higher levels of correlation are preferred. To compute the correlation values, the square roots of R^2 values are used.
- **corrvalue**(*#*) specifies the degree of correlation between the target variable and the testing variable required to be eligible for selection. Variables with higher levels of correlation are preferred. To compute the correlation values, the square roots of (pseudo) R^2 values are used. For continuous target variables, linear (OLS) models are estimated using `regress`. For categorical targets, `mlogit` is used. While lowering the correlation threshold will produce more potential candidates, their benefit may be lower.
- **gain**(*#*) specifies the amount of additional information a testing variable must contribute for a given target variable. The gain is defined as the share of cases

with missing values on the target variable that have a valid value on the testing variable. Ideally, the gain equals 1 (100%), and values closer to 1 are preferred.

- **maxmiss**(#) specifies the maximum allowable amount of missingness in a testing variable relative to the target variable. Ideally, auxiliary variables have no missing values. However, some degree of missingness can be tolerated. If this share is too high, subsequent lasso models may fail to converge because too little information is available. The default value of 0.15 allows a testing variable to have a share of missing values that is 15% larger than the share of missing values in the target variable.
- **nonlinear**(#) automatically tests for nonlinear effects of continuous testing variables. While correlation typically assumes a linear association between two variables, quadratic effects are common in empirical data, implying that associations may be (inverted) U-shaped. These effects are tested using regression models by including a squared term of the testing variable. Users specify the percent (not percentage points) improvement in R^2 (or the correlation) that the squared term must contribute to be selected as a nonlinear auxiliary. For example, if this value is set to 0.05 (5%), all squared terms of continuous predictors that improve R^2 by at least 5% are considered.
- **catlimit**(#) provides a heuristic for identifying categorical testing variables when many candidates are evaluated and manually declaring each categorical variable using the `i. prefix` is impractical. If the number of levels is equal to or below the specified limit (the default is 7), the testing variable is declared with the `i. prefix` and treated as categorical. This rule of thumb has important limitations (for example, geographical identifiers with many levels), and users should manually declare relevant variables when necessary.
- **saving**(filename) saves the final results as a `.dta` file.
- **folds**(#) specifies the number of folds used for the lasso cross-validation (CV) procedure. A larger number of folds generally yields more stable and precise results but increases computational time. For details, see `lasso`.
- **seed**(#) sets the random-number seed. Because lasso relies on randomness, results may vary across repeated calls to `auxfinder`, even with identical data. Setting a seed ensures reproducibility.
- **skiplasso** omits the computation of lasso models for final validation. This option substantially increases computation speed, as the lasso models are by far the most time-consuming component of the command. It should be used when computation times are prohibitive. In this case, final results are based solely on correlations and case counts.
- **elasticnet** computes elastic net validation models instead of lasso models. For details, see the elasticnet manual page.

- **lassoopts**(string) allows users to pass arbitrary options to customize the estimation of lasso or elasticnet models.
- **noisily** displays additional output from the regression and lasso models to provide users with more detailed insight into the computations performed.

3 Examples

In this example, we demonstrate the use of **auxfinder**. First, we load the NHANES2 dataset and recode one residual category of a variable to missing, so that these values are eligible for imputation and for the search for auxiliary variables. In this application, the analytical goal is to predict an individual's health status using various blood measurements. These target variables, all of which contain missing values, are specified first. Next, the option *testvars()* defines the variables that are evaluated as potential auxiliaries. To test every variable in the dataset, users can simply specify *_all*. In the case of the Stata NHANES2 dataset, however, several recoded variables are already included, implying that many variables appear in duplicate form. To avoid confusion, we therefore exclude these derived variables and restrict the set of candidates to variables ranging from *sampl* to *lead*.

Although categorical variables can be declared manually using the *i.* prefix, in this example we delegate the task of detecting categorical variables to **auxfinder**. We also set a random-number seed, because lasso and elastic net rely on random resampling of the data and results may therefore differ across runs. In addition, we specify that potential nonlinear effects of continuous testing variables should be examined. A value of 0.05 indicates that, once a squared term of a variable is added to a model, the model fit must improve by at least 5% for the squared term to be considered beneficial. In applied settings, this threshold would likely be set to a higher value. All remaining options are left at their default settings.

```
. webuse nhanes2, clear
. replace hlthstat = . if hlthstat == 8
(14 real changes made, 14 to missing)
. auxfinder hlthstat albumin vitaminc copper hdresult ///
> , testvars(sampl - lead) seed(123) nonlinear(0.05)
Part 1/5 done
Part 2/5 done
Part 3/5 done
Part 4/5 done
Part 5/5 done
```

targetvar	testvar	nvalid	catvar	corr_miss	corr_value	infogain
albumin	age	10351	No	.	0.310*	1.00
albumin	hgb	10351	No	.	0.319*	1.00
albumin	region	10351	Yes	0.224*	.	.
copper	sex	10351	Yes	.	0.362*	1.00
copper	tibc	10351	No	.	0.342*	1.00
copper	tibc ²	.	No	.	0.364*	1.00
hdresult	location	10351	No	0.189*	.	.
hdresult	location ²	.	No	0.234	.	.
hdresult	sampl	10351	No	0.188	.	.
hdresult	sampl ²	.	No	0.234*	.	.
hdresult	strata	10351	No	0.194*	.	.
hdresult	strata ²	.	No	0.267*	.	.
hlthstat	age	10351	No	.	0.369*	1.00

```
* Selected by lasso      ∅ lasso failed
Strong continuous auxiliary variables (0):
Strong categorical auxiliary variables (0):
Strong squared auxiliary variables (0):
Weak continuous auxiliary variables (5):
age hgb tibc location strata
Weak categorical auxiliary variables (2):
region sex
Weak squared auxiliary variables (3):
tibc sampl strata
```

After completing all steps of the procedure, the results are presented in a concise summary table. We observe that, although *hlthstat* was included in the command, it does not appear in the results. This indicates that no auxiliary variables were identified for this target variable that meet the specified correlation thresholds. For the target variable *albumin*, three auxiliary variables are identified. The first is age, which has 10,351 valid observations. The algorithm correctly classifies this variable as continuous, as it has far more than seven levels. Although age does not predict the missingness status of albumin (the *corr_miss* column contains no value and therefore falls below the prespecified threshold of 0.15; see the options discussed above), it is correlated with albumin itself, with a correlation of approximately 0.310 (corresponding to an R^2 of about 0.096) in the bivariate model. The asterisk indicates that the lasso model, which serves as the second validation step, also retains this variable as a final predictor,

suggesting that it is a stable auxiliary variable. The value of *infogain* (1.00, or 100%) shows that all cases with missing values on albumin have a valid age value, which is a favorable outcome. Because age predicts albumin itself but not its missingness status, it is classified as a weak auxiliary variable in the conclusive selection reported below the table. Turning to *region*, we see that the command correctly classifies this variable as categorical, as it has only four levels. This variable predicts the missingness status of albumin but does not correlate with its observed values.

Regarding the second target variable, *copper*, we observe that both *tibc* and *tibc*² are selected. Because *tibc* is a continuous variable, **auxfinder** tests for potential quadratic effects. In the bivariate model specification, including the squared term of *tibc* improves the model fit from 0.342 to 0.364, which exceeds the specified threshold of 5%. For the target variable *hdresult*, several noteworthy results emerge. In this case, **auxfinder** classifies *strata* as a continuous variable because it has many distinct levels (31, which is substantially larger than the specified limit of 7). However, *strata* represents sampling strata and should therefore be regarded as a nominal, rather than a continuous, variable. Interestingly, the results suggest that some structure remains in the data, as higher values of *strata* are correlated with the missingness status of *hdresult*. Nevertheless, it is advisable to manually declare *strata* as a categorical variable in a subsequent call to **auxfinder** to assess the stability of the results. Doing so also prevents the estimation of nonlinear effects, which are automatically excluded for categorical predictors in Stata.² This example underscores that users should not rely uncritically on the output of **auxfinder** but should instead examine the results carefully and make informed decisions. Such judgment typically requires substantive knowledge of the dataset as well as of the theoretical mechanisms underlying the research question.

If a numerical value of *corr-miss* or *corr-value* is shown with the symbol #, this indicates that the specified lasso or elastic net model did not converge and therefore produced no results. There are several possible reasons for convergence failures. The most common cause is an insufficient number of observations, particularly when many testing variables are included. In some cases, setting the option *maxmiss()* to zero can help, although this does not always resolve the issue. If convergence problems persist, it may be useful to manually remove testing variables, especially when they are highly correlated with one another or conceptually dependent. Another potential cause is that too many, or conversely too few, variables are included in the final selection. In any case, when a model fails to converge for a given variable, it is generally advisable either to inspect the output in detail using the *noisily* option or to reconstruct the relevant models manually. For example, for the target variable *copper*, the corresponding command would be `lasso linear copper sex c.tibc##c.tibc`, followed by a call to *lassocoeff*.

4 Discussion

In this section we give some general advice for the usage of **auxfinder**.

2. As it turns out, when the option is changed to *testvars(i.strata houssiz - lead)*, the predictive power of *strata* increases to 0.345 for *hdresult*, making it the sole predictor for this target variable.

- It is recommended to declare variable types manually. Categorical variables should be prefixed with `i.`, while continuous variables do not require a prefix. Special care should be taken when specifying target variables. In particular, binary variables should *not* be declared with the `i.` prefix, as lasso cannot be applied to them in that form. Since binary variables generally perform well in linear model specifications, it is preferable to include them without the prefix. For ordinal variables, such as Likert-scale items, there is no clear consensus: declaring them as categorical will exclude them from lasso tests, so this represents a trade-off. Furthermore, continuous target variables use `regress` to compute R^2 , whereas categorical targets use `mlogit` to compute pseudo R^2 , which can differ substantially; this makes proper declaration important. Nominal variables, however, must always be declared with the `i.` prefix to obtain meaningful results.
- As with `mi impute`, `auxfinder` considers only the system missing value (`.`) as missing in target variables. Extended missing values (`.a`, `.b`, `.c`, etc.) are ignored and must be manually recoded before using `auxfinder`.
- Depending on the number of testing variables specified and selected, computation of the lasso models can be time-consuming. To reduce runtime, users may decrease the number of folds (10 is usually sufficient), although this reduces the precision and stability of the results. If this is insufficient, the `skiplasso` option allows users to omit lasso models entirely, in which case `auxfinder` reports only correlations without validating them.
- Users should be aware that, in some cases, adding auxiliary variables to an imputation model can actually worsen results (Thoemmes and Rose 2014). Because this requires a detailed theoretical understanding of the variables and their causal relationships, `auxfinder` cannot account for such effects. Users should therefore carefully build and evaluate their imputation models even after using `auxfinder`.

5 Conclusion

Missing data remain a pervasive challenge in empirical research, particularly in survey-based studies with complex variables and low response rates. Auxiliary variables can substantially improve imputation quality by providing additional information that is not captured in the analytical model. The `auxfinder` command provides a systematic, data-driven approach to identify promising auxiliary variables, combining correlation checks with optional lasso or elasticnet validation to ensure stability and relevance. While the command streamlines variable selection, careful user judgment is still essential: variable types, theoretical considerations, and potential causal relationships should guide final imputation models. By facilitating the efficient and informed inclusion of auxiliaries, `auxfinder` can enhance the reliability of multiple imputation or full-information maximum likelihood analyses, ultimately supporting more robust empirical conclusions.

6 References

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